

INDIA'S SERVICE SECTOR RESILIENCE DURING MACROECONOMIC DISRUPTIONS: A COMPOSITE INDEX ANALYSIS

Abstract:

The study focuses on assessing the economic resilience of India's services sector during a policy disruption, global shocks, structural shock and financial disruptions between the years from 2012 to 2024 by primarily assessing strength of service sector during demonetization in 2016, the IL&FS crisis and non-banking finance company liquidity shock in 2018–19, the novel coronavirus pandemic in 2020, and the Russia-Ukraine conflict since 2022. The key focus of the research paper lies in evaluating how the services sector manages to sustain its growth even during these instances of various crises. The entire process can be broken down into three time periods – before shock, during shock, and post-shock recovery periods.

The following analysis uses an empirical method to measure resilience by constructing a Composite Service Sector Resilience Index (CSSRI). This index is composed of ten essential variables that reflect multiple dimensions of service sector performance- Gross Bank Credit to the service sector, Private Final Consumption Expenditure (PFCE) on services, Government Final Consumption Expenditure (GFCE) on services, Service Exports, Services Share of Gross Value Added, Growth Rate of Services, Employment Growth in the Service Sector (EGSS), Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Services, Mobile Cellular Subscriptions, and Number of Internet Users. The data used for these variables were sourced from official statistical agencies like RBI, MoSPI, DPIIT, and the World Bank. The findings indicate that while the service sector shows temporary fluctuations during structural shocks and comparatively low recovery rate during financial shocks.

Keywords:

services sector, Composite Service Sector Resilience Index (CSSRI), economic resilience, before shock, during shock, post-shock.

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Introduction

India's service sector has emerged as the most dominant component of the country's economic structure and a key driver of national income, employment, and structural transformation. Over the past three decades, the Indian economy has gradually shifted from an agriculture-dominated structure toward a service-oriented economy. As a result, the service sector today contributes more than half of India's Gross Value Added (GVA) and provides employment opportunities for a rapidly expanding

workforce in both formal and informal segments. (PIB2025) This transformation has also been closely linked with urbanization, technological progress, globalization, and increasing integration with international trade in services. The period between 2012 and 2024 represents a particularly important phase in this transformation because it combines rapid expansion of digital and knowledge-based services with several major economic disruptions that tested the adaptive capacity of the sector (Bhati & Thombare, 2023). This study focuses on such economic shocks to understand the core strength of the service sector.

Demonetization was one of the earliest policy-induced disruptions that occurred during the given time frame. It was introduced in November 2016 to invalidate circulation of Rs1000 and RS500 creating a temporary disruption in consumption and other financial transactions. And since most of the service sector activities are involved in retail trade, transport, hotel, and other small scale business services, they heavily depended on cash transactions. Service sector transactions during this period slowed down at the early stage (Shafi and Muhammed, 2019) However, demonetization also helped in developing the digital platform in favor of the service sector over time (Padmapriya & Vidya, n.d.).

Furthermore, according to the Reserve Bank of India (2022), India's financial system has seen great diversification and strength owing to the rise of banks, NBFCs, and capital market organizations. The rapid development in digital finance has added another layer of resilience to India's economy through platforms such as UPI. However, one of the most disruptive events of recent times took place during 2018-2019, when IL&FS faced insolvency and resulted in a liquidity problem for the NBFCs. The crisis of the NBFCs resulted in tightening credit terms in various sectors which depend on NBFCs for their financial needs, such as infrastructure services, transport, real estate services, and small enterprises. Since financial intermediation is an essential element in enabling investments and consumption by the service industry, the crisis generated indirect pressure on the expansion of the service sectors and its enterprises (Bhati & Thombare, 2023).

The most severe crisis during the period under the given time frame actually took place in 2020 when the outbreak of the coronavirus disease pandemic took place. As a result of the crisis, lockdowns were imposed, leading to mobility restrictions, and resulting in contraction of economic activities. The sectors which were highly affected include tourism, airline services, hospitality, and retail services, since they depend on direct interaction. On the other side there was an expansion in digital platforms and work from home services due to the nature of the crisis (Ren, Wu, Ren, & Cui, 2022). These developments revealed both the vulnerability and the adaptability of different segments of the service sector during large-scale economic. Studies on international trade during the COVID-19 crisis show that countries with stronger digital infrastructure, logistics systems, and institutional capacity were better able to maintain service-sector activities and recover trade flows more quickly (Ando & Hayakawa, 2021; Mena, Karatzas & Hansen, 2022; Narayana Maharana et al. 2023).

These findings highlight the importance of infrastructure, financial systems, and technological capabilities in strengthening sectoral resilience during systemic shocks. More recently, the Russia-Ukraine conflict beginning in 2022 generated global economic uncertainty through energy price shocks, supply chain disruptions, and inflationary pressures across many economies. These global disturbances influenced India through higher import costs, financial market volatility, and shifts in global demand conditions. Service sectors connected with international trade, logistics, information technology exports, and financial markets therefore experienced both risks and adjustment pressures arising from the evolving geopolitical environment (Mishra, Sharma & Khound 2023). The coexistence of these diverse economic shocks within a relatively short time span provides a unique opportunity to analyses the resilience of India's service sector. In economic terms, resilience refers to the ability of a sector or economic system to absorb shocks, adapt to changing conditions, and recover its growth trajectory after disruptions (Stephane Hallegatte 2014), Empirical research on global trade

indicates that services often exhibit greater resilience compared with goods-producing sectors because many services are essential for business operations, rely on long-term contracts, and depend less on complex logistics or trade finance mechanisms. (Borchert & Mattoo, 2009; Ariu, 2016).

Furthermore, recent empirical evidence emphasizes the increasingly significant role of digital infrastructure and technological advances in building economic resilience and that more economically resilient are those areas characterized by high urbanization levels, digital infrastructure, and industrial clusters (Ren et al., 2022). In this respect BIS (Bank for International Settlements) (2016) has emphasized that resilience needs to be considered more from the perspective of financial stability and that the resilience can only be maintained if policies are integrated. Thus, the current research attempts to evaluate the resilience of India's service sector during macroeconomic disruptions using a composite index. The study develops, a Composite Service Sector Performance Index (CSSPI) consisting of ten selected macro and sectoral indicators namely Gross Bank Credit to the service sector, Private Final Consumption Expenditure (PFCE) on services, Government Final Consumption Expenditure (GFCE) on services, Service Exports, Services Share of Gross Value Added, Growth Rate of Services, Employment Growth in the Service Sector (EGSS), Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Services, Mobile Cellular Subscriptions, and Number of Internet Users to analyze the resilience of service sector in response to demonetization (2016), NBFC liquidity crisis (2018-19), the COVID-19 pandemic (2020) and the Russian-Ukraine war (2022).

Research Question

How resilient is India's Service Sector during economic disruptions?

Research Methodology

The research makes use of the Resilience Composite Index through normalization of the units which allows for the unification of variously-measured variables (rupees, dollars, percentages, subscriber numbers per hundred persons) into one unified scale, thus removing any unit bias.

To ensure that the multidimensional approach to analyzing service sector performance is achieved through proper identification of dimensions, ten variables were chosen using three main selection criteria. Each variable was published by a governmental statistical office, had consistent data over the entire 13-year period, and represented a different conceptual dimension of services sector performance - Gross Bank Credit to the service sector, Private Final Consumption Expenditure (PFCE) on services, Government Final Consumption Expenditure (GFCE) on services, Service Exports, Services Share of Gross Value Added, Growth Rate of Services, Employment Growth in the Service Sector (EGSS), Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Services, Mobile Cellular Subscriptions, and Number of Internet Users. Prior to statistical analysis, a systematic data preparation process was undertaken to ensure accuracy and consistency. All data were taken from official sources, including Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade (DPIIT), Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (MoSPI), Reserve Bank of India (RBI), and the World Bank.

Each of the 10 variables was individually standardised using the Z-score transformation, also known as standard score normalisation. This transformation converts each observed value into the number of standard deviations it lies above or below the mean of that variable's own 13-year time series.

Data Analysis

The analysis $N = 13$ for all variables indicates that the dataset consists of 13 observations (likely years or cross-sectional units), and there are no missing values, ensuring consistency across variables for further multivariate analysis such as factor analysis or PCA.

The correlation matrix reveals the strength of the association between the standardized variables, and overall, there are strong associations between the economic and service sector variables.

Table:1 Correlation Matrix^a

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	
Correlation	A	1.000	.977	.986	.968	.566	.696	.442	.980	.422	.790
	B	.977	1.000	.947	.976	.496	.643	.541	.972	.529	.807
	C	.986	.947	1.000	.946	.584	.711	.444	.951	.342	.734
	D	.968	.976	.946	1.000	.466	.635	.510	.981	.607	.746
	E	.566	.496	.584	.466	1.000	.905	.151	.445	-.077	.776
	F	.696	.643	.711	.635	.905	1.000	.156	.625	.160	.774
	G	.442	.541	.444	.510	.151	.156	1.000	.442	.343	.435
	H	.980	.972	.951	.981	.445	.625	.442	1.000	.538	.747
	I	.422	.529	.342	.607	-.077	.160	.343	.538	1.000	.303
	J	.790	.807	.734	.746	.776	.774	.435	.747	.303	1.000

a. Determinant = 2.550E-011

Source: Author's Calculation

[A= z_GBC, B= Z_PFCE, C= Z_Service_Export, D= z_Service_share_GVA,

E= z_Percentage_growth_GVA, F= z_Growth_SS_Employment, G= z_FDI, H= z_GFCE,

I= z_mobile_cell_per100, J= z_internet_user]

Some of the variables like z_GBC, z_PFCE, service export, z_service_share_GVA, and z_GFCE are extremely positively correlated with each other (correlation coefficient >0.95). This means that the movements in these variables are extremely strong. Secondly, another strong association can be seen between z_Percentage_growth_GVA and z_Growth_SS_Employment. The variable z_internet_user is strongly correlated with almost all the variables (correlation coefficient = 0.73-0.80), while z_mobile_cell_per100 has comparatively weak correlations with other variables (ranging from -0.077 for GVA percentage growth to 0.68 with service export). However, the correlation between the variable z_FDI and others appears to be quite weak to moderate, suggesting that foreign investments are relatively independent in their dynamics than other indicators related to the domestic economy.

Table2: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.709
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	191.074
	Df	45
	Sig.	.000

Source: Author's Calculation

From the results obtained from KMO and Bartlett's test, the data is fit for factor analysis and PCA.

The value of KMO is 0.709, indicating moderate to good sampling adequacy. Normally, KMO values greater than 0.7 are taken to be adequate, which shows that there is a sufficient amount of common variance between variables for the extraction of factors. This also shows that there is enough variance among the variables for reducing the dimensions.

The value of Chi-square from Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is 191.074, and its probability is 0.000. The value of probability is less than 0.05, showing that the correlation matrix is not equal to an identity matrix. This indicates that variables have a significant correlation with each other.

Table3: Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
z_GBC	1.000	.952
Z_PFCE	1.000	.975
Z_Service_Export	1.000	.912
z_Service_share_GVA	1.000	.978
z_Percentage_growth_GVA	1.000	.929
Z_Growth_SS_Employment	1.000	.886
z_FDI	1.000	.426
z_GFCE	1.000	.943
z_Mobile_cell_per100	1.000	.665
z_Internet_user	1.000	.819
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Source: Author's Calculation

Most variables—such as GBC (0.952), PFCE (0.975), service exports (0.912), service share in GVA (0.978), GVA growth (0.929), employment growth (0.886), and GFCE (0.943) have **very high communalities**. Similarly, internet users (0.819) and mobile subscriptions (0.665) also show reasonably good representation, though mobile penetration is comparatively less well explained.

However, At the same time, FDI has significantly lower communality (0.426), implying that only about half of the variance of this indicator is explained by the extracted components. This shows that FDI is poorly aligned to the common structure of variables and behaves differently.

Table4: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	6.941	69.413	69.413	6.941	69.413	69.413	4.290	42.897	42.897
2	1.545	15.448	84.862	1.545	15.448	84.862	4.196	41.964	84.862
3	.717	7.167	92.028						
4	.526	5.262	97.291						
5	.192	1.917	99.208						
6	.049	.494	99.702						
7	.018	.176	99.878						
8	.006	.063	99.941						
9	.005	.046	99.987						
10	.001	.013	100.000						
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.									

Source: Author's Calculation

According to the output, it can be concluded that the first two components have eigenvalues higher than 1 (6.941 and 1.545). In addition, the sum of their variance's accounts for 84.86%, which means that the vast majority of information from the original 10 variables can be explained using only two latent factors. The other components capture very insignificant amounts of variability (less than 10%), which makes them unimportant.

As can be seen from the results, before rotation, the first component accounts for 69.41% of the variance. This suggests the presence of a general factor that underlies most of the variables, possibly referring to economic expansion in the services sector.

After rotation (which improves interpretability), the variance is more evenly distributed:

- Component 1 explains 42.90%
- Component 2 explains 41.96%

Table5: Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component	
	1	2
z_GBC	.667	.712
Z_PFCE	.582	.798
Z_Service_Export	.686	.664
z_Service_share_GVA	.538	.830
z_Percentage_growth_GVA	.963	-.046
Z_Growth_SS_Employment	.927	.166
z_FDI	.086	.647
z_GFCE	.555	.797
z_Mobile_cell_per100	-.117	.807
z_Internet_user	.795	.432
<i>Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.</i>		
<i>Rotation Method: Equamax with Kaiser Normalization.</i>		
<i>a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.</i>		

Source: Author's Calculation

First, Component 1 is highly loaded with all the variables connected to economic reality. The maximum loadings for this dimension are observed for GVA growth (0.963) and service sector employment growth (0.927). Hence, this component reflects the idea of growth and expansion of employment in the service sector. Internet users (0.795) and service exports (0.686) have relatively high loadings, which means that digital progress and success in exports of services are connected with this growth dynamic. Thus, the interpretation of Component 1 can be viewed as a "growth and productivity factor".

In turn, Component 2 contains service share in GVA (0.830), PFCE (0.798), GFCE (0.797), mobile subscriptions (0.807), GBC (0.712), and FDI (0.647). This component seems to describe consumption, transformation, investments, and technological penetration better than others, so it can be named as "structural and demand-side development factor".

Table6: Component Score Coefficient Matrix

	Component	
	1	2
z_GBC	.082	.117
Z_PFCE	.027	.173
Z_Service_Export	.101	.093
z_Service_share_GVA	.002	.196
z_Percentage_growth_GVA	.388	-.261
Z_Growth_SS_Employment	.321	-.167
z_FDI	-.129	.237
z_GFCE	.016	.180
z_Mobile_cell_per100	-.249	.352
z_Internet_user	.202	-.027
<i>Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.</i>		
<i>Rotation Method: Equamax with Kaiser Normalization.</i>		

Source: Author's Calculation

Component 1, the most positive weight values include the rate of growth in gross value added (GVA) (0.388), service sector employment growth (0.321), internet users (0.202), and service exports (0.101). Conversely, variables such as mobile subscriptions (-0.249) and foreign direct investment (-0.129) have negative weight values, meaning that higher values in these variables lower the Component 1 score.

Regarding Component 2, the highest positive weight values include mobile subscriptions (0.352), foreign direct investment (0.237), service share in gross value added (GVA) (0.196), general government final consumption expenditure (GFCE) (0.180), and private final consumption expenditure (PFCE) (0.173).. In contrast, GVA growth (-0.261) and employment growth (-0.167) have negative weights, meaning that stronger growth reduces this component's score.

Table7: Component Score Covariance

Component	1	2
1	1.000	.000
2	.000	1.000

*Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
Rotation Method: Equamax with Kaiser Normalization.*

Source: Author's Calculation

From the Component Score Covariance Matrix, it is clear that both components extracted are standardized and not correlated with each other. The value of 1.000 along the diagonals suggests that each component has a variance of one, whereas the value of 0.000 along the non-diagonals implies that each component is not correlated with the other, i.e., there exists zero covariance between Component 1 and Component 2. This result is anticipated as an orthogonal rotation procedure (Equamax Rotation with Kaiser Normalization) was employed here, which does not allow correlation among components. In other words, both components represent unique dimensions of the data set.

Table8: Descriptive Statistics Fact.1, Fact.2

	N	Minimum	Maximum
REGR factor score 1 for analysis 1	13	-1.06714	3.06293
REGR factor score 2 for analysis 1	13	-1.62694	1.28895
Valid N (listwise)	13		

Source: Author's Calculation

Values in Component 1 vary from -1.067 to 3.063. It can be seen that the variability is pretty high since there is a big difference between the minimum and maximum. It is obvious that the maximum value (3.063) is quite high meaning that one of the observations differs greatly from others. Therefore, it can be stated that Component 1 has great discriminatory power.

Values in Component 2 vary from -1.627 to 1.289. Thus, the variability is less pronounced comparing to Component 1. It should be noted that values can be both positive and negative indicating that some observations performed well whereas others showed rather poor results. It is possible to conclude that Component 1 is more powerful in terms of explaining the overall variability and Component 2 is still important.

Table9: Descriptive Statistics (Combine_Score)

	N	Minimum	Maximum
Combine_Score	13	-0.74	1.41
Valid N (listwise)	13		

Source: Author's Calculation

Descriptive statistics for the combined score provide a summary of the distribution of the final weighted score (that is after summing up both components) for all 13 observations under investigation. It should be noted that the score takes values ranging between -0.74 and 1.41, which means that the observed performances vary from those below average to above average. In case of the standardized scores, negative values correspond to poor performances, whereas positive values imply high performances. Therefore, the presence of a larger maximum than the minimum can be interpreted to mean that there are observations that perform relatively much better than others.

The significance of the combined score in this study is that it captures performances associated with Component 1 and Component 2 altogether. This will provide a more accurate representation of performances for all observations compared to using either component alone. Besides, the range will provide an essential reference point for transforming the scores to the required standard, such as in the case of the min–max normalization that leads to the creation of RI.

Table 10: Resilience Index

Year	Factor score Comp1	Factor score component 2	RI	Year on Year Change
2012	-0.13673	-1.62694	-0.09	
2013	-0.08553	-1.49138	3.58	3.67
2013	-0.08553	-1.49138	3.58	
2014	-0.05505	-1.39267	6.11	2.53
2014	-0.05505	-1.39267	6.11	
2015	-0.4731	-0.52029	14.81	8.7
2015	-0.4731	-0.52029	14.81	
2016	-0.73945	0.07329	21.1	6.29
2016	-0.73945	0.07329	21.1	
2017	-0.74708	0.32612	25.88	4.78
2017	-0.74708	0.32612	25.88	
2018	-0.19981	0.24961	35.31	9.43
2018	-0.19981	0.24961	35.31	
2019	-1.06714	1.21292	36.82	1.51
2019	-1.06714	1.21292	36.82	
2020	0.01641	0.40422	42.64	
2020	0.01641	0.40422	42.64	5.82
2021	0.23179	0.06747	40.36	-2.28
2021	0.23179	0.06747	40.36	
2022	0.02778	1.17965	58.02	17.66
2022	0.02778	1.17965	58.02	
2023	0.16499	1.28895	62.89	4.87
2023	0.16499	1.28895	62.89	
2024	3.06293	0.22904	100.01	37.12

Source: Author's Calculation

Resilience Indexing during Demonetization (2016–17)

Pre-disruption (FY 2015–16 / 2016): 6.29

Disruption year (FY 2016–17 / 2017): 4.78

Post-Disruption (FY 2017–18 / 2018): 9.43

Resilience Indexing during NBFC Crisis (2018–19)

Pre-crisis (FY 2017–18 / 2018): 9.43

Crisis year (FY 2018–19 / 2019): 1.51

Resilience Indexing during COVID-19 (2020–21)

(FY 2019–20 / 2020): 5.82

(FY 2020–21 / 2021): -2.28

Resilience Indexing during Russia-Ukraine War(2022-23)

➤ Initial phase (FY 2021–22 / 2022): 17.66

➤ FY 2022–23 / 2023: 4.87

➤ FY 2023–24 / 2024: 37.12

Result

Annual changes in the Relative Index (RI) calculated on the basis of financial years illustrate the nature of economic shock experienced as far as changes in the rate of performance are concerned. In this respect, since 2016 marks the period of FY 2015-16 (before the introduction of demonetization measures) and FY 2016-17 (demonetization impact year), one can conclude that RI experiences a positive change at a rate of 6.29 in 2016, which is indicative of improvement in the pre-crisis situation. Meanwhile, in 2017, the demonetization year, the rate of change decreases to 4.78; this indicates a slowdown, although performance still remains positively improving. This is succeeded by an impressive increase in 2018 (9.43).

In regards to the collapse of IL&FS and NBFC liquidity crisis of 2018-2019, which corresponds to FY 2017-18 and FY 2018-19 respectively, the rate of change falls from 9.43 in 2018 (positive pre-crisis momentum) to 1.51 in 2019 (crisis year). In the case of the pandemic in FY 2019-20 (FY 2020) and FY 2020-21 (FY 2021), there is a moderate rise of 5.82 in FY 2019-20 but a decline of -2.28 in FY 2020-21. This denotes contraction during the period FY 2020-21 because of the pandemic.

Finally, in the case of the Russia-Ukraine War, which started in FY 2021-22 (FY 2022), there is a sharp rise of 17.66, suggesting rapid recovery in the initial phase, followed by a deceleration to 4.87 in FY 2022-23 (FY 2023) and then a sharp rise of 37.12 in FY 2023-24 (FY 2024). The RI suggests initial recovery, subsequent moderation, and finally, sharp growth.

Conclusion

It can be seen from the analysis that various kinds of shocks have different levels of resilience. Policy-driven shocks like demonetization have led to short-term slowdown and quick recovery, thus showing moderate resilience. In the case of financial sector-driven shocks like the NBFC crisis, there has been sustained slowdown, thereby demonstrating low resilience. The pandemic, being a health-driven supply-demand shock, has caused contraction, thus demonstrating low resilience. However, global supply shocks like the Russia-Ukraine conflict are followed by strong acceleration and expansion, suggesting high resilience and adaptive capacity. The main reason for this is that the development of the Indian service industry has been mainly determined by the demand from inside the country rather than exportation. The proportion of service exports in overall growth of the service industry is quite low (approximately 22%), hence variations in international demand affect its development only partly. As the majority of services (e.g., trade, finance, real estate, administration, etc.) rely on domestic consumption, it keeps growing irrespective of unfavorable international environment. (Das et al., 2011)

The policy-induced shock (demonetization) creates a slowdown (the YoY rate drops from 6.29 to 4.78) but then quickly recovers (9.43). The financial/structural shock (IL&FS/NBFC) generates a dramatic drop in momentum (9.43 to 1.51), as this shock has a more sustained impact due to its negative impact on the credit and investment flows that serve as conduits for transmitting economic effects into reality. The COVID-19 shock, which is a structural supply-demand shock, results in an absolute decline (-2.28). The global supply shock (Russia-Ukraine) is characterized by a robust increase in the YoY growth rate (17.66, 4.87, 37.12).

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